

A Critique of the Climate Change Legal Regimes

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Introduction

Ever since the Industrial Revolution, human activity has been the major driver of environmental change (Tong et al., 2022). In pursuance of legitimate economic interests like agriculture, forests are cleared to create more farmland to grow crops to feed the ever-growing population. Considering that forests are carbon sequestrators (Nzabarinda et al., 2025), this has the effect of reducing the forests' carbon storage capacity. Similarly, in order to produce energy to power residential, commercial, and industrial sectors, fossil fuels such as coal are burnt to produce energy. Yet, when fossils are burnt, they release carbon dioxide, a major greenhouse gas (GHG) which traps heat from the sun. Such interferences with the natural environment by humans have increased concentrations of GHGs in the atmosphere and excesses in their levels have interfered with the earth's assimilation ability, thereby causing atmospheric temperatures to rise beyond normal levels – a phenomenon which causes climate change. Some of the observable effects of climate change include rising global temperatures, increased intensity and frequency of cyclones and tropical storms, sea-level rises, droughts, changes in precipitation patterns, shifts in species distribution and the emergence of new vector-borne diseases (Rawat et al., 2024, Mishra et al., 2010).

According to Manatsa (2018), the growing realization of the negative impacts of climate change has prompted the international community to act with a view to eliminating or at least mitigating them. One way of achieving this was the development of rules and incentives aimed at reducing emissions. In 1988, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was created by the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) to provide scientific information that was to serve as the basis for an international legal response. In 1990, the IPCC produced its 1st Assessment Report predicting a severe warming up of the earth and called on the international community to address the problem. As stated by Manatsa (2018), the report paved way for negotiations that culminated in the adoption of an international treaty in the form of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) – an international legal response from which the Kyoto and Paris Protocols emanate. Together, these three serve as the core legal instruments for multilateral action against climate change. Yet, despite their adoption, climate-change concerns have deepened and global emissions have continued to escalate. This strongly suggests that the Climate Change Legal Regimes (CCLRs) are either failing or have not served their intended functions. It is against this backdrop that the shortcomings of the

current legal frameworks need to be investigated to uncover areas where laws are not achieving their intended goals.

Negotiations in the lead up to the UNFCCC

Before examining the intricacies of the UNFCCC and its protocols, it is pertinent to look at the drafting history of the Convention. Such drafting history is key to understanding the difficulty of achieving climate action. As will be more fully addressed in the discussions to follow, the negotiations in the lead up to the UNFCCC were not only difficult, but also took time to conclude owing to the interplay of conflicting interests between and amongst the participating states (Wold, Hunter and Powers 2009, p.135). Because different countries have varying interests in climate action, depending on such factors like their levels of economic development, reliance on fossil fuels, geographical vulnerability to climate change impacts, political priorities, issues like emission reduction targets, binding commitments and burden sharing on the basis of equity, all created significant disagreements with no clear path forward. Developed countries pushed for stricter binding commitments, while developing countries were concerned about the economic burden of the stringent emission caps and the extent to which this could forestall development. The question of how to equitably distribute the burden of climate action was also a thorny issue, with developing countries arguing that the industrialized countries should take greater responsibility since they were responsible for the current atmospheric mess (Hunter, Salzman and Zaelke, 2011, p.674). Such ethical concerns brought about a deadlock, which almost threatened the negotiations. The disagreement between the developed countries and the developing countries over who should bear the burden of climate action is commonly known as the North-South impasse – this was partially resolved when the participating states incorporated the principle of Common But Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR) in the final text of the UNFCCC. Be that as it may, the North-South impasse has remained a point of contention seeing that climate change negotiations are largely determined by historical imbalances and ethical considerations.

Beyond the North-South impasse, further divisions emerged between and amongst the participating states, where countries had diverse interests and/or priorities. Because they are highly vulnerable to sea-level rises and coastal flooding, the Alliance of Small Island States (AOSIS) supported an agenda for an agreement that was aimed at compensating small island states against the adverse impacts of climate change (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.404). Unlike the island states, the oil-producing and exporting countries (OPECs) were concerned about the potential economic losses resulting from declining demand in fossil fuels due to climate action and were determined to block any future agreement that was aimed at reducing the global oil demand (Hunter et al., 2011, p.675).

Against all odds, the UNFCCC was adopted in 1992. However, competing interests led to the adoption of a compromise agreement which merely suggested controls in place of binding obligations. This partly explains why the UNFCCC has struggled to keep the world on course to achieving a low-carbon trajectory.

Enter the UNFCCC

The UNFCCC is the foundation for multilateral action against climate change (Danish, 2007, pp.10-15, pp.76-77). The Convention was adopted on 9 May 1992 and entered into force on 21 March 1994 (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.56). It sets as its objective the stabilization of GHG ‘concentrations at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system’ (Art.2 of the UNFCCC). Such a level was to be achieved within a time frame sufficient enough to allow ecosystems to adapt naturally to climate change while ensuring that food production is not threatened, and enabling development to proceed in a sustainable manner (Art.2 of the UNFCCC).

Environmental principles contained in the UNFCCC

The UNFCCC recognises principles such as the ‘no harm’ principle, the CBDR, the precautionary principle, the inter-generational and intra-generational equity principles. To an extent, these principles are key to understanding why the CCLRs are failing to discharge their mandate as some have their own weaknesses. The principles are explained in greater detail below.

The ‘no harm’ principle

The ‘no harm’ principle is a principle of international environmental law requiring that countries must ensure that activities within their jurisdiction do not cause damage to the environment of other states or of areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction (Principle 21 of the Stockholm Declaration; the Trail Smelter Case (United States v Canada). The rule plays a central role in climate change mitigation by establishing a legal and ethical duty for countries to reduce their GHG emissions as they play a part in global climate change and could potentially harm other countries through climate change impacts. Notwithstanding, there are limitations in using the ‘no harm’ principle in addressing climate change (Mayer, 2016, pp.79-104). As will be evident, the ‘no harm’ principle has shown itself to be an inadequate remedy in countering the vagaries of climate change.

The CBDR principle¹

This principle recognizes the fact that all countries have a duty to undertake climate change intervention measures, but their responsibilities depend on their capacities and differing national circumstances (CISDL, 2002). Realistically, the principle has two implications. First, it acknowledges the need for all countries to undertake climate change intervention measures because climate change impacts are widespread and may not be confined to specified regions (CISDL, 2002). Secondly, it recognizes the fact that different countries have contributed to the climate problem in different ways and have differentiated capacities to address the problem (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.56). In accordance with this view, developed countries have a primary if not a greater responsibility to take action in light of their historic emissions (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.56).

The precautionary principle

This principle states that lack of scientific certainty or definitive proof of harm should not be used as a reason to postpone the invocation of any measures as may be necessary to prevent such harm. It prioritizes prevention over having to wait for significant harm to happen before action can be taken. For example, it may be better to switch to renewable energy sources than relying on fossil fuels in order to mitigate climate change. While it is a good thing to prioritize prevention over cure, it should be remembered that taking preventive measures can put a strain on a country's finances.

The inter-generational and intra-generational equity principles

Within the realm of climate change, 'intergenerational equity' entails that the present generations have a legal and moral duty to protect the earth's climate and to mitigate the negative effects of climate change that will turn out to be detrimental to the future generations. The principle plays a role in raising public awareness about climate change impacts and the need to take into account the future generations when framing legislation and policy frameworks. The 'intra-generational equity' principle is concerned with how the burdens of climate change action are distributed within the present generation. It presupposes that no country should disproportionately bear the costs of climate action while others free ride on the works and/or efforts of others.

State obligations under the UNFCCC

Under the UNFCCC, states have the obligation to protect the earth's climate from human-induced climate change. This duty stems from the widespread scientific acceptance that human activities are the key drivers of climate change (Lynas et al., 2021), and if action is not taken, there will be disastrous consequences. This obligation requires international cooperation to mitigate emissions, yet, this cooperation faces obstacles such as conflicting national priorities and implementation hurdles. This

¹ See Art.3 (1) of the UNFCCC.

explains why countries were categorized into groups under the UNFCCC based on the principle of CBDR, recognizing that different countries have varying capacities to address the challenge. In keeping with this principle, parties to the UNFCCC were identified as:

- ◆ **Annex I countries** – comprising the highly industrialized countries such as Australia, Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America.
- ◆ **Annex II countries** – comprising the developed countries with an obligation to provide financial assistance to developing countries, including Austria, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland and Spain.
- ◆ **Developing countries** – comprising developing and Least Developed Countries (LDCs) with limited capacity to undertake climate action.

The above notwithstanding, the UNFCCC required the participating countries to develop national inventories of anthropogenic emissions and facilitate the removal by sinks of these gases from the atmosphere (Art. 4 (1) (a) of the UNFCCC), to formulate and implement climate change mitigation measures (Art. 4 (1) (b) of the UNFCCC), to promote the development, application and diffusion of technologies that control anthropogenic emissions (Art. 4 (1) (c) of the UNFCCC), to undertake cooperation in adaptation to the negative impacts of climate change (Art. 4 (1) (e) of the UNFCCC), to promote and cooperate in education and educational training related to climate change (Art. 4 (1) (i) of the UNFCCC). In addition, the developed countries were required to provide financial assistance to the developing countries to enable them to implement the objectives of the Convention (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.58).

Institutional arrangements under the UNFCCC

To establish a framework for global cooperation and action, the UNFCCC established a number of institutions including the following:

- ◆ **The Conference of the Parties (COP)** – whose role is to periodically review the obligations of states and the institutional arrangements under the Convention, facilitate the exchange of information and assess the effect of climate change intervention measures, and to make recommendations as may be necessary for the implementation of the Convention (Art. 7 of the UNFCCC).
- ◆ **The Secretariat** – whose function is to facilitate the flow of information and provide the organizational support necessary for the implementation of the Convention (Art. 8 of the UNFCCC).
- ◆ **The Subsidiary Bodies for Scientific and Technological Advice** (Art. 9 of the UNFCCC) **and for Implementation** (Art. 11 of the UNFCCC) – these have the function of providing technical advice to the COP on all matters affecting the implementation of the Convention, including the scientific assessment of the climate change intervention measures.

The Kyoto Protocol of 1997

It is worth noting that even with the adoption of the UNFCCC in 1992, it soon became apparent that the Convention was bound to fail owing to the difficulty in achieving consensus regarding ambitious target setting and burden sharing (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.58). The CBDR principle, while designed to promote burden sharing on the basis of equity, brought about the perceived failure of the UNFCCC by hindering the development of a binding legal instrument due to disagreements over how to operationalize it. As argued by Manatsa (2018), this resulted in the adoption of a framework convention which merely suggested controls in place of binding obligations. By 1995, negotiations to strengthen the existing framework were launched (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.58). These negotiations led to the adoption of the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 (Yamin and Depledge, 2004, p.421). Given that the Kyoto Protocol operationalized the UNFCCC, it set as its objective the stabilization of GHG emissions 'at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system'. However, Kyoto broke new ground by setting legally-binding targets for the developed countries which the UNFCCC lacked (Thornton and Beckwith, 2004, p.58). It required the developed countries to cap their emissions by 5%-7% below the 1990 levels between the years 2008 and 2012 (Art. 3 (1) of the Kyoto Protocol). It also operationalized the CBDR principle by requiring the developed countries to commit to binding obligations while excluding the developing countries (Art. 10 of the Kyoto Protocol).

When the Kyoto Protocol was adopted, countries agreed that the first commitment period was to run from 2005 to 2012 after which they would agree on a new global instrument. Despite its implementation in 2005, the general view was that the Protocol was facing a bleak future (Rosen, 2015). Boston (2008) notes that focus was already shifting towards what was to happen after 2012. At COP13 in Bali, Indonesia, countries agreed to a roadmap which launched negotiations to come up with more ambitious targets (Ullal, 2013). However, the Bali climate talks failed because of disagreements over the nature of binding commitments, with the US, Japan, and Canada strongly opposed to significant emission cuts, while the developing nations pushed for stronger commitments from richer countries owing to their historic contribution to the problem (Christoff, 2008; Boston, 2008). The extent of the contribution of Annex II countries and the level of ambition required to put the world on course to achieving a low-carbon trajectory, were also key points that prevented parties from reaching an agreement (Boston, 2008). These issues were meant to be finalized by 2009 at COP15 in Copenhagen, Denmark.

When countries eventually met in Copenhagen in 2009, focus was on finding a solution on the outstanding issues. However, the Copenhagen talks collapsed due to disagreements between the developed and developing nations on emission reduction targets, with US and China unwilling to commit. This led to the adoption of a non-

binding Copenhagen Accord. Despite not having legal force, the Copenhagen Accord, however, recognized the need to limit global temperatures below 2 degrees Celsius (Para. 2 of the Copenhagen Accord); to submit their emission reduction targets by January 31, 2010 (Paras. 4 and 5 of the Copenhagen Accord), and developed countries also pledged to help developing countries with climate financing (Para. 8 of the Copenhagen Accord).

Having failed at COP 15 in Copenhagen, the participating states reconvened at Cancun, Mexico in December 2010 to settle outstanding issues. This Conference may have addressed Copenhagen's failings but once again, countries disagreed on key issues. As could be expected, countries failed to agree on long-term emission reduction targets, as well as on procedures and parameters for sector-specific agreements (Sands and Peel, 2012, p.298). Following an anticlimactic finish at Cancun, countries met again in Durban, South Africa in 2011 to chart the path forward. The participating states agreed to a new treaty by 2015 (Hill, 2011, p.96). However, the Durban Platform did not achieve much as the agreement was not enforceable. As observed by Manatsa (2018), the only significant part of the Durban negotiations was the commitment made by some developed countries to the second commitment period under the Kyoto Protocol. This second commitment was adopted in Doha, Qatar, in 2012 (Ritter and Casey, 2012), and was to run for eight years (from 2012-2020). But even so, the ultimate goal of reducing emissions was not achieved because of limited participation by major emitters such as the US, Russia and Canada, the lack of legally binding commitments for developing countries, and reliance on flexibility mechanisms that allowed countries to significantly avoid their emission reduction targets.

Classification of Parties under the Kyoto Protocol

Much like the UNFCCC, and in keeping with the CBDR principle, the Kyoto Protocol categorized countries into two groups as follows:

- ◆ **Annex I countries** – comprising the highly-industrialized nations, including countries with economies in transition. These had binding commitments under the Protocol.
- ◆ **Non-Annex countries** – comprising developing countries. These had no binding commitments under the Protocol.

Institutional arrangements under the Kyoto Protocol

Just like the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol adopted the COP whose function is to oversee the implementation of the Protocol. It also adopted a Secretariat (established under Art. 8 of the UNFCCC) to serve as the Protocol's Secretariat (Art. 14 of the Kyoto Protocol). Besides, it adopted the Subsidiary Bodies for Scientific, Technological Advice and Implementation (established under Arts. 9 and 10 of the UNFCCC) to also serve as technical and advisory bodies for the implementation of the Protocol (Art. 15 of the Kyoto Protocol).

The Paris Protocol of 2015

The Paris Protocol is an international legal instrument that was adopted in December 2015 at COP21 in Paris, France to replace the Kyoto Protocol past its expiration in 2020. The Paris Protocol seeks to strengthen the global response to the threat of climate change by limiting the global average temperatures to well below 2°C, while pursuing efforts to limit temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels (Art. 2 of the Paris Protocol). To achieve this goal, the Protocol enjoins the participating countries to build resilience around adaptation and mitigation (Art. 2 of the Paris Protocol). Put differently, it encourages member states to reduce GHG emissions and to adjust to the current and expected impacts of climate change by undertaking measures as may be necessary to minimize harm and reduce vulnerability.

The agreement is composed of both mandatory and non-binding commitments. On one hand, it imposes binding obligations on the developed countries and encourages them to continue undertaking climate change intervention measures while capping their domestic emissions (Art. 4 (4) of the Paris Protocol). On the other hand, the Protocol is based on 'Nationally Determined Contributions' (NDCs), a policy setting which considers a country's national priorities and/or circumstances (Art. 3 of the Paris Protocol).² Thus, unlike the UNFCCC and its Kyoto Protocol which imposed emission reduction targets on specific countries, the Paris Agreement uses a bottom-up approach whereby countries set their own targets. This *laissez faire* approach raises questions about the Protocol's effectiveness seeing that it leaves national governments with room for manoeuvre, to undertake climate action based on their unique circumstances. Whereas NDCs can be hailed for enabling countries to tailor their climate change intervention measures based on individual circumstances and economic capabilities, it is noteworthy that they may not serve any purpose where member states table modest emission reduction targets.

Much like the UNFCCC and its Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Protocol also implements the CBDR, and acknowledges that the Agreement will be implemented in the light of different national circumstances (Art. 2 (2) of the Paris Protocol). Be that as it may, the Protocol uses the terms 'Common But Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities (CBDR-RC)' (Art. 2 (2) of the Paris Protocol), but unlike the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol, it includes provisions for climate finance to the developing countries for climate change mitigation and adaptation (Arts. 9 and 11 of the Paris Protocol).

² See Art. 3 of the Paris Protocol as read together with Arts. 4, 7, 9, 10, 11 and 13 of the same Protocol.

The shortcomings of the current CCLRs

It is pertinent to note that the CCLRs have not achieved much by way of action as global emissions have reached record highs in the past few years. The coming into force of the UNFCCC and its protocols sparked hope that the international community would rise to the challenge but, alas, that was not the case, as global emissions have continued to rise. This raises concerns about the effectiveness of the CCLRs. In the discussion to follow, regard is paid to the shortcomings of the CCLRs. Identifying these gaps is crucial because it allows for improvements to be made to the existing structures to make the laws more effective in achieving their goals.

Shortcomings of the UNFCCC

As previously mentioned, the UNFCCC aims to achieve the ‘stabilization of GHGs at a level that would prevent ‘dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system’ (Art. 2 of the UNFCCC). This was to be achieved while ensuring that food production is not threatened, and enabling development to ‘proceed in a sustainable manner’ (Art. 2 of the UNFCCC). While Art. 2 of the UNFCCC can be seen as an attempt to reconcile the goals of environmental protection with those of economic development, it is important to note that ensuring such development does not deplete natural resources is not as simple as it seems. Indeed, it is difficult to picture how economic development goals could be realized without exacerbating global climate change (Stern 2015). This is not to suggest that it is not possible – it is. However, achieving economic development without worsening global climate change is difficult as most developing countries still rely on fossil fuels to generate energy and alternatives to fossil fuels may not be readily available. To add to this, most countries lack the necessary technological and financial resources required to transition to low-carbon pathways. Also, given a choice between economic development and environmental protection, many developing countries may prioritize economic needs over climate action, and may be reluctant to invest in green initiatives.

In addition to the above, the diction used in Art. 2 of the UNFCCC can also be criticized for being too vague. It is important to note that the phrase ‘dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system’ is nebulous, thereby leaving room for divergent interpretations of the level of change that would be considered dangerous. Indeed, it can be argued that defining dangerous anthropogenic interference ‘is a complex task that can only be partially supported by science, as it involves normative judgments’ (Oppenheimer, 2006, pp.1399-1407). Different countries may come up with their own interpretations of ‘dangerous anthropogenic interference’, based on political, legal, ethical and cultural considerations – this may allow countries to come up with weaker mitigation measures. Yet, choices related to Art. 2 determine the level of change that should be set as a common goal for policy interventions and have implications for future pathways (IPCC Fourth Assessment Report, Climate Change 2007).

Linked to the above, the word ‘stabilization’ preferred in Art. 2 of the UNFCCC is not ambitious enough. While the word stabilization can be loosely interpreted to mean reducing, and whereas both terms are aimed towards improving the earth’s climate system, it is crucial to highlight that ‘stabilization’ is more concerned with maintaining GHG emissions at current levels while preventing future emissions, while ‘reducing’ concerns efforts at capping emissions down to a lower level. Seeing that the emphasis is on stabilization and not reduction of GHGs, it’s as if the intention was for the Convention to allow for continued emissions at current levels, yet this was not the case. Besides, Art. 2 does not outline specific emission reduction targets, not even timeframes within which countries were expected to achieve them. This made it very difficult to measure progress by the participating states, let alone to hold them accountable for inaction.

Apart from the above, the UNFCCC can be criticized for over-emphasizing the role of the ‘no-harm’ rule in combating global climate change. While the principle offers a valuable framework for holding states accountable by establishing the obligation to prevent activities which may cause environmental harm to other countries, it has been asserted that the ‘no-harm rule’ has been rendered an antiquated remedy in addressing climate change and its impacts (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.421). Indeed, its effectiveness is and can be limited by challenges in attribution of harm and allocation of responsibility. Given the transboundary nature of GHG emissions, it is not only difficult to trace their origins and to apportion blame and/or responsibility (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.421). Once the GHGs are in the atmosphere, it may be difficult to pin the blame on anyone. Besides, the ‘no harm rule’ seeks to maintain a balance between a state’s right to exploit the environment and the responsibility to avoid harming other countries, yet most countries may prioritize economic development over the duty not to harm others (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.421). Also, climate change impacts may manifest over vast stretches of time, making it very challenging to attribute liability under the ‘no harm’ principle (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.421). By the time climate change impacts manifest themselves, it would be difficult if not impossible to know who may have been responsible for them. What is more, alternatives to fossil fuels are and may not always be readily available or affordable (Nanda and Pring, 2012, p.421). This is true for most OPECs and Less Economically Developed Countries (LEDCs), who may not have invested in clean energy or may find it very difficult to do so, thereby raising the thorny issues of CBDR and CBDR-RC.

Moreover, the UNFCCC’s exemption of the developing countries from binding commitments has created rifts between the developed and the developing countries. One point of contention has been the push by the developing countries calling upon the industrialized countries to take the lead in addressing climate change, to pay for their historic climate debt. Another area of dispute has been burden sharing on the basis of equity. While there have been efforts to address the North-South impasse, it is noteworthy that inequalities have remained and this continues to be an issue in

international relations today. The UNFCCC's perceived breakdown could perhaps be attributed to its failure to impose binding obligations on the participating states. Whereas a liability approach could have worked, the UNFCCC avoided it in favour of international cooperation. Yet, history has shown that the international community is still lacking in coordinated action – the North-South impasse is an indictment. The inability to bridge this divide suggests that the global community is not working together effectively to address climate change. It reflects a collective and persistent failure to achieve coordinated action, highlighting the need for greater global solidarity.

Related to the above shortfalls is the fact that the UNFCCC is nothing more than a framework Convention, which provided a general structure for international cooperation against climate change, but left the specific implementation details to individual countries. A closer look at the framing of the Convention would lead one to the inescapable conclusion that it does not address the basics of climate change, especially in relation to climate change adaptation and mitigation. This is hardly surprising considering that the UNFCCC was more of a compromise, borne out of prolonged negotiations that were characterized by animosity and divisions on the part of the negotiating blocks and the participating states.

Besides, the UNFCCC can also be criticized for its lack of enforcement mechanisms. Apart from its voluntary commitments from the participating states, it is noteworthy that the bodies created to oversee its implementation, such as the COP, Secretariat, and the Technical Bodies for Scientific Advice and Implementation all lack compliance powers. Whereas Olazabal et al. (2019) argue that the development of institutions does not on its own translate into reduction of climate vulnerabilities, it can be argued that strong institutions can effectively enforce environmental regulations, ensuring that polluters are held accountable for their actions. Without strong institutions, some countries may still ignore their obligations and get away with it. This can lead to a situation where they are able to ignore their commitments under the Convention without any significant repercussions. This is a major weakness of many international legal instruments and is a problem rooted in international law itself. To put it succinctly, international law is saddled by a dearth of enforcement mechanisms – which is why scholars like Anthony D'Amato (2010) have asked if international law is really law. However, despite all these criticisms, the UNFCCC remains a key foundation, setting out the basic principles, rules, obligations and key institutions influencing contemporary action against climate change (Oberthur and Ott, 1999, p.33).

Shortcomings of the Kyoto Protocol

Just like the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol is also not immune to criticism. Its major criticism is that it did not contain binding obligations for all. In keeping with the principle of CBDR, it placed an unfair burden by setting binding obligations for developed countries such as USA and Canada while allowing the industrializing countries like China and India to continue emitting a great deal of GHG. This

undermined the effectiveness of the Protocol as a significant portion of GHG emissions coming from the industrialized countries was left unaddressed by the Protocol. Indeed, GHG emissions from Annex I countries, began to be superseded by those from the industrializing countries (Sheeran, 2007. P.704). For instance, between the years 1990 and 1998, India recorded a 57% increase in emissions, making it the 5th largest fossil fuel emitter in the world (Sheeran, 2007, p.704). Of late, China's historical emissions have also 'reached 312GtCO₂ in 2023, overtaking the EU's 303GtCO₂', making it the world's second largest emitter (Carbon Brief, 2024).

Because the agreement imposed binding obligations on developed countries while allowing industrializing countries to continue with their emissions, Kyoto targets became a bone of contention which eventually led to withdrawal of USA, Russia and Canada. In abdicating their responsibilities under the Kyoto Protocol, Russia and Canada argued that the agreement was unfair because it did not impose binding obligations on the industrializing nations, particularly China and India. As one expert notes, 'the Kyoto targets simply reflect on what was politically feasible at the time of its enactment and not what is appropriate from an ecological standpoint' (Barret, 1998, pp.20-39). Indeed, the Protocol has been overtaken by events as some countries that were once classified as developing countries have developed to such a level that they no longer fit the definitions of 'developing economies'. Besides, the fact that the developed countries were held to binding commitments when the developing countries were not, was unfair. Although the developed countries should take the lead in view of historic emissions, some would argue that developing countries also contribute to the problem, although in very marginal ways. To this end, the Kyoto Protocol ought to have assigned the developing countries their respective share of responsibility.

As argued by Manatsa (2018), the Kyoto Protocol can be blamed for its ill-considered focus on the outcome, namely the target of reducing GHG emissions by 5% to the 1990 base levels without considering the root causes of the climate problem. Instead of enacting more fundamental policy changes, for instance, by banning fossil fuel usage, Kyoto merely treated the symptoms by calling upon the participating states to cap their emissions. In the words of Blustein (2011) 'it offers the wrong diagnosis' to the climate problem since, in dealing with GHG emissions, it dealt with the symptoms, rather than the root cause, namely those activities that cause GHG emissions, including the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation.

In addition to the foregoing, Kyoto can also be blasted for ineffective targets. It is noteworthy that the targets set were not ambitious enough, particularly with major emitters such as the USA not participating. Furthermore, the Protocol's ambitious targets were expected to be fulfilled within a period of eight years (from 2005 to 2012). This was a short deadline within which the global community was expected to have made demonstrable progress in terms of emission reduction.

Although Kyoto has been lauded for its market-based approaches to emission reduction, also known as the flexibility mechanisms (including the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM),³ Joint Implementation Mechanism (JIM)⁴ and Carbon Trading (CT)⁵ (Gang, 2007; Michaelowa, 2003), there have been concerns about the flexibility mechanisms not meeting the expectations. Critics argue that the mechanisms may allow countries to buy emissions from others without reducing emissions within their jurisdictions, leading to hot-air trading which may also compromise environmental stability. Mudeme (2008), for instance asserts that, much to everyone's chagrin, the CDM has turned out to be cumbersome and unrewarding. The CDM's failure was disappointing, but this was expected considering its failure to provide criteria for choosing which projects or which countries to invest in (Ullal, 2013). Sutter and Pareno (2007), cited in Olawuyi (2010), add that no mechanism would fulfil the Kyoto Protocol's objective of capping emissions and contributing towards sustainable development simultaneously.

Regarding the JIM, it can be argued that emission-reduction projects may also be undertaken in countries that have already witnessed a decline in GHG emissions, thereby creating hot-air credits that are not characteristic of genuine emissions. As for emission trading, the Kyoto Protocol can also be criticized for its failure to clearly define the principles, rules, modalities and guidelines that underpin CT. Finally, but important, the Protocol did not stipulate any penalties for non-compliance and the institutions set under it all lacked compliance powers. In view of the shortcomings discussed above, and taking into consideration that emissions have increased in recent years, the efficacy of the Kyoto Protocol, much like the UNFCCC has been questioned.

Shortcomings of the Paris Protocol

Even though the Paris Protocol can be lauded for its near-universal participation, calling for the participation of all, including the developing countries, one could contend that the agreement has not been immune to criticism. A major criticism has been the dearth of an enforcement mechanism to hold countries accountable for meeting their targets under the agreement. It is noteworthy that the Protocol relies on the voluntary cooperation of the participating countries when implementing their NDCs, with no penalties for non-compliance.

Whereas its predecessors have provided a broad framework for multilateral action against climate change to which future agreements were expected to offer more specificity, the Paris Protocol did nothing of that sort. Instead, it introduced a new model of voluntary participation allowing countries to set their own targets and report on progress. As this *laissez faire* approach gives autonomy to national governments to

³ The CDM allows countries to invest in projects in developing countries that reduce emissions.

⁴ The JIM, allows countries to jointly implement projects that are aimed at reducing emissions.

⁵ CT allows countries that have emission units to spare to sell their surplus to those that have exceeded their limits.

formulate their own policies, including policy instruments for implementation, but without enforcement mechanisms, it may not be sufficient to achieve the Protocol's ambitious targets. One can argue that in the absence of strict consequences for non-compliance, states tend to free ride and prioritize development over environmental protection. As posited by Maizland and Fong (2025), most countries' NDCs 'are not ambitious enough and will not be enacted quickly enough to limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C'.

To add to the above, the Paris Protocol can be blamed for combining the binding elements of accountability and non-binding emission reduction targets. On one hand it imposes strict requirements, calling on the developed countries to continue undertaking economy-wide absolute emission reduction targets (Art. 4 (4) of the Paris Protocol). On the other hand, it relies on non-binding aspects, encouraging parties to submit climate action plans on a voluntary basis (Art. 5 (2) and 6 (2) of the Paris Protocol). In critical ways, it bets on the strength of rising norms like state cooperation, rather than law to achieve its purpose and for it to succeed, this gamble would need to prove successful. Yet, looking ahead, it is not very clear whether it would pay off, and being a hybrid legal instrument with both binding and non-binding commitments, it is highly likely that most countries may choose non-binding commitments which are less onerous, over binding elements which are not only difficult to achieve, but may also be costly.

Conclusion

This article examined the CCLRs with a view to laying bare their shortcomings. It found that the existing frameworks are not only weak, but have also failed to provide a tenable legal solution to the climate change problem. The UNFCCC embarked on the goal of emission reduction, but being a framework Convention, which merely suggested controls with no binding commitments, it went a short distance. Whereas the Kyoto Protocol did introduce legally-binding targets, not only did it fail to sufficiently address the long-standing issue of burden sharing on the basis of equity, but it also suffered from short-termism. While the Paris Protocol has introduced long-terms goals, it also relies on voluntary cooperation and because of that its success is improbable. Put succinctly, the efforts at collective action against climate change ushered in by the UNFCCC, its Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Protocol are not strong enough to meaningfully impact the problem. Thus, to successfully transition to a low-carbon future, deeper cuts in global emissions and a new legal solution are required. While negotiating a new law may be possible, only time will tell if the global community could rise to the challenge.

Seeing that the pace and scale of outcomes from the UNFCCC and its protocols have failed to respond to the urgency of climate change, and having identified some weaknesses within the CCLRs, the author makes the following recommendations.

First, considering that global cooperation on climate change has been hampered by the North-South impasse, a new climate change paradigm, incorporating principles of equity, collective responsibility, and sustainable development, must be created. While the promulgation of a new global framework that addresses the North-South impasse is a significant challenge due to the deep-seated historical inequalities, divergent interests, and complex political dynamics, it is not impossible because of shared goals and the evolving dynamics of global governance. Indeed, the rise of new economic powers in the Global South, including the G20 and Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS), is shifting the global balance of power, giving them more influence in international negotiations and global governance. Simultaneously, the global community is increasingly aware of the injustices faced by the Global South and the need for fairer arrangements. To effectively resolve the North-South impasse, the international community would need to move beyond a purely economic focus and embrace a more holistic approach. This involves the recognition of climate change as a global challenge – one that requires collaborative solutions, not just North-South cooperation. They ought to reframe the narrative, avoiding framing the issue as revolving around historical emissions, and focusing more on shared values, while establishing a system of accountability that reflects the interests of all nations. This will present an opportunity for countries to work together, even when they have differing interests.

Second, by building upon existing frameworks, strengthening commitments, and addressing the underlying issues of equity and justice, a more effective global climate regime can be achieved. There are so many pathways to achieving this. One way would be to strengthen the already existing frameworks with more ambitious goals. For example, the existing emissions reduction goals (the NDCs) under the Paris Protocol would need to be strengthened – given that the Paris Agreement relies on voluntary action, yet, the agreement does not have explicit enforcement mechanisms – there is a need for stronger mechanisms to ensure compliance. Another way would be to strengthen the extant frameworks with more equitable implementation. To achieve this, developed nations would need to fulfil their commitment to provide financial and technological transfers to support developing countries in their adaptation and mitigation efforts or through mechanisms for compensating the developing countries for unavoidable climate-related losses and damages. In the alternative, the developed countries need to acknowledge their historical contribution to climate change, and should be prepared to share a fairer burden of the transition to a low-carbon economy. A different approach would be for the developed nations to support developing countries in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs), such as eradicating poverty and improving infrastructure, investing in renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and hydropower – this would limit their reliance on traditional biomass, which contributes to deforestation and air pollution.

Third, considering that the current system of multilateral action against climate change relies heavily on state-level agreements and commitments, which are not only slow but

can also be easily bypassed or weakened due to prioritization of national interests over global goals, energy should be directed on building inclusive dialogue and governance. This shift should focus on building trust, promoting multi-stakeholder engagement at the national level, including civil society, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and the private sector in policymaking. The hypothesis that is put forward is that increased stakeholder engagement can lead to more robust and evidence-based policymaking as well as buy-in in terms of implementing climate action plans at the national and local levels.

Last, but not least, given that the CCLRs have been criticized for addressing the effects of climate change (capping emissions) rather than its core causes (fossil fuel usage and deforestation), there is a need for root cause action. In other words, focus should be on more impactful policies and actions, such as phasing out fossil fuels and investing in renewable energy. However, sight need not be lost as to the fact that phasing out fossil fuels and transitioning to renewable energy raises challenges for OPECs, whose economies are tied to fossil fuel exports, making a sudden shift to renewables difficult. Consequently, a just transition is needed, involving economic diversification, investments in renewable energy infrastructure and financial support to help these countries to adapt.

References

- Barrett, S. (1998). 'Political economy of the Kyoto Protocol'. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 14 (4), pp. 20-39. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/14.4.20> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Blustein, S. (2011). 'From the Bottom-Up: Redesigning the International Legal Response to Anthropogenic Climate Change'. *Adelaide Law Review*, 32 (2), pp.1-14. <https://eprints.qut.edu.au/41974/> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Bodle, R., Dona, L. and Duwe, M. (2016). 'The Paris Agreement: Analysis, Assessment and Outlook'. *Carbon and Climate Law Review*, 10 (1), pp.5-22.
- Boston, J. (2008). 'Global climate change policies: From Bali to Copenhagen and beyond'. *Policy Quarterly*, 4 (1).
- Carbon Brief (2024). *Analysis: China's emissions have now caused more global warming than EU*. <https://www.carbonbrief.org/analysis-chinas-emissions-have-now-caused-more-global-warming-than-eu/> [Accessed 21 February 2025].
- Christoff, P. (2008). 'The Bali roadmap: Climate change, COP 13 and beyond'. *Environmental Politics* 17 (3), pp.466-472.
- CISDL (2002). *A Legal Brief, for the World Summit on Sustainable Development*. Johannesburg, 24 August, 2002. <https://www.cisd.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/International-sustainable-development-law-2002.pdf> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Climate Change 2007. *Mitigation of Climate Change: Contribution of Working Group III to the Fourth Assessment Report of the IPCC*. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/ar4_wg3_full_report-1.pdf [Accessed 19 May 2025].
- Coghlan, M. (2002). 'Prospects and pitfalls of the Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change'. *Melbourne Journal of International Law*, 3(1), p.165.

- D'Amato, A. (2010). *Is International Law Really Law?*
<https://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu/facultyworkingpapers/103> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Danish, K.W. (2007). 'An Overview of the International Regime Addressing Climate Change'. *Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, Winter 2007, pp.10-15, 76-77.
- Gang, C. (2007). 'The Kyoto Protocol and the Logic of Collective Action'. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 1 (4), pp.525-557.
- Hill, T. (2011). 'UN Climate Change Conference in Durban: Outcomes and Future of the Kyoto Protocol'. *Macquarie Journal of International and Comparative Environmental Law*, 7 (2), p.92-97.
- Hunter, D., Salzman, J. and Zaelke, D. (2011). *International Environmental Law and Policy* (4th ed.). New York: Thomson Reuters/ Foundation Press.
- Joint Implementation. <https://unfccc.int/process/the-kyoto-protocol/mechanisms/joint-implementation> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Lynas, M., Houlton, B. and Perry, S. (2021). *Greater than 99% consensus on human caused climate change in the peer-reviewed scientific literature*. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ac2966> [Accessed 13 February 2025].
- Maizland, L. and Fong, C. (2025). *Global Climate Agreements: Successes and Failures*.
<https://www.cfr.org/background/paris-global-climate-change-agreements> [Accessed 27 February 2025].
- Manatsa, P. (2018). *Confronting Global Climate Change: The Continuous Search for a Tenable Legal Solution*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Midlands State University, Gweru, Zimbabwe.
- Mayer, B. (2016). 'The relevance of the no-harm principle to climate change law and politics'. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Environmental Law*, 19 (1), pp.79-104.
- Michaelowa, A. (2003). *The Kyoto Protocol and its flexibility mechanisms*.
<https://www.isecoeco.org/pdf/kyotoandflex.pdf> [Accessed 27 February 2025].
- Mishra, A.K., Singh, V.P. and Jain, S.K. (2010). 'Impact of global warming and climate change on social development'. *Journal of Comparative Social Welfare*, 26 (2-3), pp.239-260.
- Mudeme, L. (2008). 'Cement Production and Green House Gas Emission: Implications for Mitigating Climate Change'. An MSC Thesis, School of Geography, Archaeology and Environmental Studies, University of Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa.
- Nanda, V.P. and Pring, G. (2012). *International Environmental Law and Policy for the 21st Century* (2nd ed.). Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.
- Nzabarinda, V., Bao, A., Tie, L., Uwamahoro, S., Kayiranga, A., Ochege, F.U., Muhirwa, F.A. and Bao, J. 'Expanding Forest carbon sinks to mitigate climate change in Africa'. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 207.
- Oberthur, S. and Ott, H.E. (1999). 'The Kyoto Protocol: International Climate Policy for the 21st Century'. Berlin: Springer.
- Olazabal, M., Galarraga, I., Ford, J., Murieta, E.S. and Lesnikowski, A. (2019) 'Are local climate adaptation policies credible? A conceptual and operational assessment framework'. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development*, 11 (3), pp.277-296.
- Olawuyi, D.S. (2010). 'From Kyoto to Copenhagen: Rethinking the Place of Flexible Mechanisms in the Kyoto Protocol's Post 2012 Commitment Period'. *Law, Environment and Development Journal*, 6.
- Oppenheimer, M., 2006, 'Defining Dangerous Anthropogenic Interference: The Role of Science, the Limits of Science'. *Risk Analysis*, 25 (6), pp.1399-147.
- Rawat, A., Kumar, D. and Khati, B.S. (2024). 'A review on climate change impacts, models, and its consequences on different sectors: A systematic approach'. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 15 (1), pp.104-126.
- Report of the COP on its first session held in Berlin, Germany from March 28 to April 1, 1995.
<https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/cop1/07a01.pdf> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- Ritter, K. and Casey, M. (2012). *Nations extend weaker Kyoto Protocol*.
<https://www.csmonitor.com/Environment/Latest-News-Wires/2012/1208/Nations-extend-weaker-Kyoto-Protocol> [Accessed 6 June 2025].

- Rosen, A.M. (2015). 'The Wrong Solution at the Right Time: The Failure of the Kyoto Protocol on Climate Change'. *Politics and Policy*, 43, (1), pp.30-58.
- Sands, P. and Peel, J. (2012). *Principles of International Environmental Law* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Sheeran, K. (2007). 'Beyond Kyoto: North-South Implications of Emissions Trading and Taxes'. *Seattle Journal for Social Justice*, 5 (2), p.31.
- Stern, N. (2015). *Economic development, climate and values: making policy*.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2015.0820> [Accessed 15 February 2025].
- Sutter, C. and Parreno, J.C. (2007). 'Does the Current Clean Development Mechanism Deliver Its Sustainable Development Claim: An Analysis of Officially Registered CDM Projects'. *Climatic Change*, 84, pp.76-77.
- The International Institutions and Global Governance Program. *The Global Climate Change Regime*.
<https://www.cfr.org/report/global-climate-change-regime>. [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- The Stockholm Declaration of 1972
- The Sunday Morning Herald, May 29, 2011. *Kyoto deal loses four big nations*
<https://www.smh.com.au/environment/climate-change/kyoto-deal-loses-four-big-nations-20110528-1f9dk.html> [Accessed 6 June 2025].
- The text of the Copenhagen Accord.
- The text of the Kyoto Protocol.
- The text of the Paris Protocol.
- The text of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).
- Thornton, J. and Beckwith, S. (2004). *Environmental Law* (2nd ed.). Sweet and Maxwell Limited.
- Tong, S., Bambrick, H., Beggs, P.J., Chen, L., Hu, Y., Ma, W., Steffen, W. and Tan, J. (2021). *Current and future threats to human health in the Anthropocene*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106892>. [Accessed 11 February 2025].
- Trail Smelter Case (United States v Canada) (1941) 3 UNRIAA 1905 at 1965.
- Ullal, N.R. (2013). 'A successor for the Kyoto Protocol - Challenges and Options'. *New Zealand Journal of Environmental Law*, 8 (1), pp.45-56.
- Wold, C., Hunter, D. and Powers, M. (2009). *Climate Change and The Law*, LexisNexis.
- Yamin, F. and Depledge, J. (2004). *The International Climate Change Regime: A Guide to Rules, Institutions and Procedures*. Cambridge University Press.

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